

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Amnesty International

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Monitoring online violence
against high profile individuals

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Contents

1	Executive summary	2
1.1	Challenge overview	2
1.2	Data overview	2
1.3	Main objectives	2
1.4	Approach	3
1.5	Main conclusions	3
1.6	Limitations	4
1.7	Recommendations and future work	4
2	Data overview	5
2.1	Dataset description	5
2.2	Data quality issues	5
2.3	Data summary	6
3	Data visualisation	8
4	Experiments	10
4.1	Abuse detection	10
4.2	Inter-rater reliability	12
4.3	Reproducing results	14
5	Future work and research avenues	15
5.1	Completing partial analyses	15
5.2	Fixing data quality issues	16
5.3	Tweet presentation and rating	18
5.4	NLP	18
5.5	Combining human and automated judgments	18
6	Team members	19

1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

A poll commissioned by Amnesty International and carried out in eight countries revealed that 23% of women surveyed had experienced online abuse or harassment. [5] Recently, Amnesty have launched *Troll Patrol*, a crowd-sourcing project aiming to detect and measure the amount and nature of abusive tweets directed at women. [6]

The aim of this challenge is to understand how data science can be applied to the data collected as part of *Troll Patrol*, in order to better understand the phenomenon of online violence. A further aim is to find automated ways of monitoring online abuse via the use of machine learning methods.

1.2 Data overview

The dataset consists of a selection of tweets directed at about 1,000 high profile women in the US and UK. This amounts to approximately 700,000 individual tweets, including demographic information on the authors. Over 188,000 contain crowd-sourced labels, classifying tweets as *abusive*, *problematic*, or *non-abusive*. For 500 tweets, expert annotators provided labels for the severity and type of abuse.

1.3 Main objectives

The main objectives of the challenge are:

1. To develop a real-time visualisation dashboard for abusive tweets and the dynamics of the network, facilitating an in-depth exploration of the mechanisms behind online abuse.
2. To build an automated machine learning classifier that can detect abusive tweets, in order to flag them up as well as collect better statistics on the phenomenon.

3. To inform future developments of the *Troll Patrol* crowd-sourcing platform, so as to achieve a scientifically rigorous data collection process and make a more efficient use of volunteer time.

1.4 Approach

The problem of classifying a tweet as abusive or not is closely related to *sentiment analysis*, a particular kind of text classification where machine learning methods are used to classify the sentiment content of a text unit. [18, 11, 16, 17] Different forms of abuse exist [19], and to detect some of these an algorithm would require context and the ability to understand subtle cues. However, we expect that the bulk of online abuse can be detected with algorithms inspired by those used for sentiment analysis.

In light of this, we decided to explore the following two approaches. The first method makes use of heuristics, summary statistics, and machine learning to create some preliminary predictions for the dataset. The second exploits the tweets already annotated by volunteers to train a deep neural network classifier which can then categorize new, unlabeled data.

Simultaneously, we conducted a statistical analysis of the dataset to extract valuable insights on the distribution of the data and the network dynamics, which can further help with the classification and the visualisation of the results.

1.5 Main conclusions

We find that issues with the data, more specifically the annotation scheme and method, provide significant barriers for the classification of fine-grained abusive language detection. Lack of information on individual ratings prevents us from being able to compare the performance of our automated classifiers to that of human annotators. Results based on a small sample of tweets we annotated ourselves show that the deep learning classifier obtains reasonable results compared to those of

human annotators, but performance will ultimately need to be evaluated on a more reliable dataset.

By investigating the logistic classifier weights, we find that there is a sizable overlap between terms in the *abusive* and *problematic* labels.

1.6 Limitations

- No data on individual annotators was provided. There is therefore no quality control on the annotators.
- The task is highly subjective and, based on our experiments discussed in Section 4.2, we expect that there is limited agreement between annotators.
- The ratings of individual annotators were not recorded whenever a tweet was labelled by multiple people. This introduces a number of problems: most severely, more frequent annotations become biased; and assessment of inter-rater reliability is not possible.
- The dataset seems to suffer from strong selection bias, as the sampling of the annotated tweets is non-uniform. Therefore, it may not be possible to make any generalisable conclusions.
- No data exploration was recorded from the Data Study Group. This will need to be repeated for future analyses.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

Regarding data collection, we make the following recommendations:

- Information on the annotator of each rating should be stored, and clearly documented.
- Tweets should be distributed uniformly to the annotators, in order to avoid selection bias.

For future work, we suggest that:

- Amnesty should consider what metric they require the classifier to be optimised for. This will be determined by the specific application.
- Information on the annotators should be used to perform quality control on the volunteers, as discussed in Section 5.2.1. This could then be used to compute an aggregate abusiveness score.

2 Data overview

2.1 Dataset description

We were provided with a selection of circa 750,000 tweets directed at 1,000 high profile women in the US and UK. We filtered out tweets not related to this project¹, leaving us with 697,000 tweets. Of these tweets, 188,336 were annotated as either *non-abusive*, *problematic* or *abusive*, through Amnesty's *Troll Patrol* platform.

The annotations obtained by Amnesty, and provided to the group, relate specifically to a form of abuse which, while not necessarily explicit in its potential to be abusive, is directed towards an individual, making it fall under the *directed* typology, either *implicit* or *explicit*. [19]

2.2 Data quality issues

1. Lack of a data dictionary describing the specific schema and format of the dataset. This led to extra time having to be spent understanding the data, causing delays on the other phases of this project.
2. Missing information on the individual crowd-sourced labels. Even though some tweets were annotated by multiple volunteers, only a single label is ever reported, and it is unclear how it was calculated. In order to obtain reliable labels it would have been crucial to retain this information, as discussed in Section 5.2.2.

¹Filtering was based on the `source_project` field.

3. Lack of source information on the labels. There is no way of connecting judgments to the annotators that made them, making it impossible to obtain a measure of confidence in the volunteers. It was therefore not possible to reduce bias and protect against malicious annotators, as discussed in Section 5.2.1.
4. The number of times tweets have been annotated is not what one might expect from a uniform assignment—with or without replacement—as evidenced by the histogram in Figure 1, and Section 2.3.3. This form of selection bias leads to a potentially unrepresentative sample, and thus makes it hard to draw any general conclusions based on the data.

2.3 Data summary

2.3.1 Label imbalance

The data is heavily imbalanced towards the *non-problematic* class, as shown in Table 1. The fact that only 3% of tweets are labelled as *abusive* makes training abuse detection classifiers difficult.

Label	Count	% of Total
Non-problematic	162,849	86.5%
Problematic	19,785	10.5%
Abusive	5,702	3.0%

Table 1: Summary table of label counts.

2.3.2 Emotion and label relation

Each tweet in the dataset is labelled with a emotion among *anger*, *disgust*, *fear*, *joy*, *neutral*, *sadness*, and *surprise*. These labels were already present in the dataset, but no information is given on their origin. We suspect these come from a standard sentiment analysis package, such as R's `sentiment`.

We found that abusive tweets are most strongly associated with *disgust*, while non-problematic tweets are associated with *joy*.

2.3.3 Number of annotations per tweet

Figure 1: Log-linear plot of the number of annotations per tweet.

The sampling of labelled tweets appears to be highly non-uniform, as evidenced by the distribution of the number of annotations per tweet in Figure 1. The most surprising feature is the spike in the number of tweets with 17 to 29 annotations. Over 82% of tweets were annotated by a single person, over 97% were annotated by two or fewer, and over 99% were annotated by three or fewer. On the other hand, some tweets were annotated by up to 54 people.

2.3.4 Authors of abusive tweets have fewer followers

Authors of abusive tweets have less than half as many followers on average than their non-abusive counterparts. We find an average of 2,076 followers for authors of abusive tweets, compared to an average of 5,053 followers for authors of non-abusive tweets.

Figure 3: Time series analysis of abusive tweets to @SenatorCollins.

Locations The third tab shows the geographical locations that abusive tweets were sent from.

Figure 4: Location of abusive tweets sent to @HackneyAbbot.

Authors The final tab shows information on the authors of abusive tweets. This reveals that only a few accounts sent more than one abusive tweet.

4 Experiments

4.1 Abuse detection

We train two machine learning algorithms to classify tweets in the three categories of *abusive*, *problematic*, and *non-problematic*. The models take in as input the tweet’s raw text, with re-tweets removed, and are required to provide the annotated label as given in the dataset.

4.1.1 Experimental set-up

The first classifier is based on **logistic regression** and uses a simple set of features, namely: unigrams, bigrams, token counts, average token length, and document length. Data is preprocessed by replacing all URLs and usernames with `_URL_` and `_USERNAME_` tokens, and stopwords are removed. Punctuation is preserved, as users may use non-standard punctuation (i.e. multiple exclamation marks) as a vehicle to express themselves. The model is trained with an ℓ_2 penalty loss, and 10-fold cross-validation.

The second classifier uses a **deep learning** model which has been shown to perform well on a variety of linguistic tasks: the LSTM architecture [4]. Empirically, this model offers a good compromise between bias and variance, which is important given the noisiness of the dataset. As input features, we use 100-dimensional GloVe embeddings [12] trained on two billion tweets.³ The 100-dimensional LSTM output is passed to a two-layer perceptron with rectified linear units and a 200-dimensional hidden layer, and is finally classified by a softmax layer. For performance reasons, the dataset is split into test/development/training sets, with the test and development sets each being made up of 10,000 tweets, and the remaining tweets forming the training set. Models are selected based on development set performance (F-score on the *abusive* class). We use a cross-entropy loss function, and optimised using Adam [8]. Due to the high imbalance of the data, naively training with cross-entropy leads to a very low recall of abusive tweets. In

³Available from <https://nlp.stanford.edu/projects/glove/>

order to stop the non-abusive tweets from drowning out the training signal, we use a class-weighted cross-entropy function which downweights the cost of positive errors for over-represented data. The weight for each class is set as the inverse of the fraction of total tweets of that class. We evaluate on the test set, reporting precision, recall, and f-score.

4.1.2 Results and discussion

We find that our **logistic regression** model performs extremely poorly on recall for the *problematic* and *abusive* labels, as evidenced by the top row of Table 2. It clearly prefers to label items as *non-problematic*, suggesting that there simply are not enough *abusive* and *problematic* tweets in the dataset. By checking the classifier weights, we inspect which features are most discriminative. We find that, when classifying something as *non-problematic*, the model unsurprisingly relies on the presence of positive terms such as “great” and “congrats”. For the *abusive* and *problematic* labels, the classifier relies on negative terms such as “ugly”. We see a large overlap in the most discriminative terms for these two labels, suggesting that terms alone may not be useful in prediction of fine-grained labels, as they do not allow for enough context. As the top 30 discriminative terms for *abusive* and *problematic* tweets overwhelmingly consist of negative terms, we see that robust identification of sentiment may provide a good signal for this specific form of abuse.

Model	Precision			Recall			F-Score		
	no	pr	ab	no	pr	ab	no	pr	ab
Logistic regression	90	38	21	97	16	5	93	22	8
Deep learning	96	16	85	61	55	60	74	25	67
<i>Always</i> no	87	–	–	100	0	0	93	–	–
<i>Always</i> ab	–	–	3	0	0	100	–	–	6

Table 2: Precision, recall, and F-scores on the *non-problematic*, *problematic*, and *abusive* labels for the two models and the baselines.

The best-performing **deep learning** model used downweighting of over-

represented classes in order to counter the imbalance of the data, and fine-tuned its word embeddings. Regularisation was achieved via weight decay, with a weight of 0.001. By changing the cross-entropy weights for each label, it is possible to train models optimised for recall or precision on specific labels. Results for a model with weights equal to the inverse of the fraction of total tweets with the label are shown in Table 2. We see an increase in recall for both the *problematic* and *abusive* classes.

In order to give more context to these numbers we also report, at the bottom of Table 2, the performance of two simple baselines: one that always reports the majority-class, i.e. *non-problematic*; and one that always reports tweets as *abusive*.

We further note that, given the different training regimes for the two models, these numbers do not allow a direct comparison between the deep learning and logistic regression classifiers.

Finally, we trained the same deep learning model on a binary classification task, where the problematic and abusive labels were merged into one.

Label	Precision	Recall	F-Score
Non-problematic	93	86	90
Problematic & Abusive	41	60	49

Table 3: Performance of deep learning model on binary classification.

4.2 Inter-rater reliability

4.2.1 Experimental set-up

When training machine learning systems for classification, it is essential to have an understanding of the difficulty of the task for humans, as well as the agreement between the labels of different annotators (known in the literature as *inter-rater reliability*). As the data necessary to estimate these metrics was not available, we ran a small experiment to provide us with a rough estimate of the difficulty of the task.

We selected a set of 10 *non-problematic*, 10 *problematic*, and 10 *abusive* tweets uniformly at random from the dataset, and asked the members of our group to label them independently. The annotators were only shown the contents of the 30 tweets, shuffled, and were asked to label them according to the guidelines given on the *Troll Patrol* website⁴. We then used a number of metrics to gauge the inter-rater reliability, and the agreement of our annotations with the ones provided in the dataset.

4.2.2 Results and discussion

We found an inter-rater reliability between the members of our group of 0.37, as measured by either Fleiss's κ or Krippendorff's α . Interpretation of these numbers in isolation is hard, but as a general guideline a $\kappa < 0.40$ is classified as *poor* according to Fleiss, [3] and a $0.21 < \kappa < 0.40$ is classified as *fair* by Landis and Koch. [9] In order to get a more intuitive idea, in Figure 5 we show a box plot of the distribution of annotator precision and recall of the dataset annotations, split by class. As can be seen from the figure, the median recall for both the *problematic* and *abusive* labels are below 50%. No single group member was able to label as *abusive* more than six out of the 10 tweets that had been labelled as *abusive* in the dataset.

We then combined the labels from all group members using a simple majority-class rule, and calculated the inter-rater reliability between these labels and the ones in the dataset. We find a value of 0.45 as measured by either Fleiss's κ or Krippendorff's α .

Finally, we also used our top-performing deep learning model to annotate the same 30 tweets. Performance with respect to dataset labels is shown in Figure 5, with a red dot. We further measured the inter-rater reliability between the deep learning model and the dataset labels, and found a Fleiss's κ of 0.45 and a Krippendorff's α of 0.46. This shows that the deep learning classifier compares well to the performance of human annotators. Its agreement with the dataset labels is close to the performance of a group of human annotators using a majority-class criterion.

⁴The guidelines were retrieved on 18th April 2018.

Figure 5: Precision and recall of group members with respect to the dataset annotations. Figures for *non-problematic*, *problematic*, and *abusive* labels are reported separately. The red circles indicate the performance of the deep learning model.

4.3 Reproducing results

All neural network code can be found under the `nlp/` directory. Please refer to the `nlp/README.md` file for instructions on how to set up the environment, the requirements, and how to train the models.

The inter-rater reliability code is in the `annotation_task/` directory. The main script is `annotation_task/iaa.py`.

The interactive dashboard was written in R using the `shiny` package, and can be found under the `NetworkAPP/` directory.

5 Future work and research avenues

5.1 Completing partial analyses

Given the exploratory nature of this challenge and the limited time available, it was not possible to conduct or complete a number of useful analyses. We list here the most important ones, which we recommend be completed in future work.

In Section 4.1.2, we reported precision and recall values for one particular trained instance of each of our classifiers. It is often possible to increase one at the cost of the other, by varying the classification threshold. In our deep learning model this is additionally achieved by varying the weights in the loss function, as discussed in Section 4.1.1. It is therefore not possible to state in general that a pair of precision and recall values is better than another. In order to provide a more complete picture of the performance of the models and enable better comparisons, we recommend plotting the precision-recall curves, the ROC curves, and calculating the areas under them. [2]

In Section 4.2, we compared the performance of the deep learning classifier to that of human annotators. The same experiment should be run with the logistic regression classifier, as well as the baseline classifiers.

Finally, the two classifiers were trained and evaluated in different ways: the logistic regression model used cross-validation, while the deep learning model used a test/development/training split. However, the models should be compared as much as possible on equal grounds. For future work, we recommend finding estimates of the generalisation error for both models that are comparable.

5.2 Fixing data quality issues

5.2.1 Quality control based on annotator profile

Language and cultural variation, as well as an awareness for subtle cues in the combination of different forms of media, is fundamental to detect abuse online. The cultural and contextual information required to understand abuse makes this a hard task for machine learning approaches, and generally large datasets are required. Crowd provided labels have been shown to be a reliable method to collect such datasets. [15] However, these crowd provided labels have to be carefully assembled and evaluated to reduce bias and protect against malicious, adversarial raters. In settings where the crowd is comprised of volunteers, a balance between ease of access and reliability of the ratings has to be struck, to ensure that enough data can be collected.

To enable Amnesty to acquire high-quality ratings, different approaches can be taken, depending on what data about the crowd should be stored and how liberal Amnesty wants to be about who to allow as a rater. Independent of the approach taken, future label acquisition should focus more on the individual ratings and the background of the raters in terms of their accuracy and intentions. It is crucial to preserve individual ratings, as well as any information available about the raters.

The current dataset lacks information on the individual differences in ratings of the same tweet, or even the set of tweets rated by an individual. Given that raters will differ in their culture and sensitivity to issues of abuse, tracking some information about raters offers great potential. It can be used to evaluate the individual ratings provided (how trustworthy is a particular rater, how coherent are individual ratings for a particular topic of tweets), which tweets to assign to raters (e.g. if a particular rater has a lot of experience in general, or for a particular topic) and identifying raters with malicious intent (spammers, trolls, etc.).

One option would be to require volunteers to provide personal information before allowing them to rate, which could span from basic demographic information to a full verification system. This would lead to highly reliable and trusted raters, and might increase their motivation. However, the more involved sign-up process would also reduce the number of volunteers, and

some raters may simply not be comfortable with sharing such information. Furthermore, issues of personal information and identifiability might be more important than improving annotations to Amnesty.

If a direct evaluation of raters is not desired, indirect measures of rater evaluation should be adopted. As a bare minimum, individual unique identifiers for rater sessions (such as browser cookies, or similar) should be kept. To identify the reliability and intention of the raters indirectly, a validation process (much like ReCaptcha⁵) could be adopted. Raters in this scenario would be provided a fixed amount of “ground truth” tweets, for which the correct labels are already known, and their reliability and intent could be extrapolated on the basis of the ratings. For example, if a rater does not rate a set of tweets as offensive, which Amnesty believe are offensive, we should be cautious about ratings provided by such a user. This approach could be adaptive, conditional on the number of tweets rated by the user. For example, a subset of the first tweets could be comprised of “ground truth” tweets, to establish if the user understands the tasks and is a troll or spammer. If the user continues to provide ratings, such an adaptive system would provide an ever larger proportion of challenging tweets.

5.2.2 Aggregating crowd ratings

Since a lot of variability exists in the evaluation, as evidenced in Section 4.2, it is beneficial to get multiple ratings for all tweets. Currently, this is not the case: most tweets are only rated by one annotator, while a subset of tweets is rated by a disproportionate number of users. We recommend that tweets be distributed uniformly at random to annotators. This would lead to a more reliable data collection process, as well as a more efficient use of volunteer time.

Once multiple ratings have been acquired, they need to be aggregated into a single label. Currently, no information is given on how this was done for the dataset. Due to the uncertain nature of the task, aggregation should not follow a majority vote, as it his would lead to a small majority of unreliable and infrequent raters determining the outcome. A simple

⁵<https://www.google.com/recaptcha>

improvement would be to introduce weights of reliability for raters, e.g. established by “ground truth” tweets. [1] More sophisticated approaches can be followed, which take into account label uncertainty. [20]

5.3 Tweet presentation and rating

Giving more context to volunteers, in the form of related tweets, would enable better judgments of the abusiveness of a message. Providing a way to reevaluate a tweet after an erroneous rating is submitted could improve the data, and offer a more satisfying user experience. Finally, for tweets that have been labelled as *abusive*, it would be useful to have volunteers explain what the specific nature of abuse is.

5.4 NLP

One of the core aims for future work is to improve classification on the *abusive* and *problematic* classes. This can be achieved by providing the classifiers with better training data. As evidenced by the inter-rater reliability experiment in section 4.2, this is an inherently difficult task, and even human annotators have difficulty agreeing on labels.

With better training data, it will be possible to look at more sophisticated NLP methods. One approach for future work would be the use of different kinds of embeddings, specifically embeddings trained on noisy data that is likely to contain a great deal of abuse. Other deep learning architectures that could offer a performance boost, given adequate training data, are bidirectional LSTMs, Tree-LSTMs, as well as other models that have been shown to work well on sentiment classification tasks. [17, 13, 10]

5.5 Combining human and automated judgments

Bayesian model averaging constitutes a promising direction for future developments, [7] and would allow Amnesty to combine classifications provided by volunteers with those of machine learning methods. Such an

approach could be generalised further, by including the allocation of human labels as part of the algorithm [14] – which would allow the crowd to focus on the more challenging tweets, while leveraging automatic methods for the less critical cases.

6 Team members

Pushkal Agarwal is a PhD student at King’s College London, funded by a Sir Richard Trainor scholarship. His work is in the field of social media data analytics and machine learning using R and Python.

Cheuk Ting Ho is a Data Scientist at Inawisdom. With 5 years research experience in quantum physics, she is skilled in computational quantitative analysis and machine learning modelling. She worked on the exploratory data analysis, and helping the team understand the data.

BingZhang Hu is currently a research associate at Open Lab, School of Computing, Newcastle University. His research interests include the computer vision, machine learning and deep learning.

Jean Maillard is a PhD student at the University of Cambridge, department of Computer Science and Technology, working on natural language processing. He is interested in machine learning, deep learning, and ethical and policy issues relating to artificial intelligence. For this project, he worked on the deep learning and inter-rater reliability experiments.

Mridul Seth is a research assistant at ICTEAM, UCLouvain working on diffusion in complex networks.

Lucia Siciliani is a PhD student at the University of Bari in Italy. Her research is focused on question answering over knowledge bases.

Reham Al Tamime is a PhD student at the University of Southampton. She works on understanding the reactions of Wikipedia contributors during new disease outbreaks. She is interested in interdisciplinary research to tackle anti-social behaviours online.

Natalie Thurlby is a PhD student at the University of Bristol. Her

research in computational biology focuses on predicting the function of human genes and proteins. Natalie contributed to the data exploration and future work.

Pablo Leon Villagra is a PhD student at the University of Edinburgh. His research in cognitive science contrasts learning in humans and machines to better understand the representational and computational basis of cognition. Pablo contributed to the data exploration and data wrangling. He then explored different ways how to improve the aggregation of ratings and how machine learning algorithms can be combined with crowd-sourced ratings to detect abusive online content.

Zeerak Waseem is a PhD student at the University of Sheffield. He works on abusive language detection and is interested in the ethical and sociological considerations required to tackle the problem of hate speech and online abuse.

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